

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CLINICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES AND FUNCTIONAL DIAGNOSIS OF TRAUMATIC OCCLUSION

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Abstract

Modern periodontists agree that occlusal disorders are risk factors for the occurrence of focal inflammatory and dystrophic processes, and in generalized periodontitis they significantly aggravate the course and worsen the treatment prognosis. The multifactorial nature of the pathogenesis of generalized periodontitis necessitates the use of an interdisciplinary approach; orthopedic methods aimed at eliminating traumatic occlusion play an important role in complex treatment.

Keywords: generalized periodontitis, traumatic occlusion, occlusal diagnostics.

Relevance of the topic Generalized periodontitis is a common pathology leading to early loss of teeth, worsening the functional state of the dentoalveolar apparatus and indicators of the quality of life of a person [1]. Progressive atrophy of the bone tissue of the alveolar processes disturbs the balance and leads to pathological tooth mobility, deformation of the dentition and functional disorders in various parts of the dentition [3]. Orthopedic treatment is carried out in order to normalize occlusal relationships, prevent, eliminate or reduce the functional overload of the periodontium [4]. Atrophy of the alveolar bone in periodontitis leads to secondary displacement of the teeth, deformation of the dentition and the development of traumatic occlusion [5]. Overload disrupts periodontal trophism, accelerates the progression of resorption and leads to pathological tooth mobility [6]. The combination of functional overload with endogenous factors and the impact of microflora significantly accelerates the process of atrophy [7]. It is proved that the physiological load contributes to the normal trophism of the periodontium and the preservation of its structure and function. In a healthy periodontium, due to the presence of numerous anastomoses between the vessels, conditions are created for the effective redistribution of blood during chewing, which is facilitated by the changing tension of the periodontal fibers and the configuration of the interfiber spaces [8]. With age, the reserve capacity of the periodontium decreases. The weakening of the permeability of the walls of blood vessels in various diseases and age-related changes leads to a violation of the shock-absorbing and trophic function of the periodontium, which is an endogenous factor leading to organic

changes in its tissues [9]. Exogenous factors of periodontal tissue damage include inadequate hygiene and exposure to pathological microflora, partial loss of teeth, primary iatrogenic and non-iatrogenic occlusion disorders [11]. A decrease in the reserve endurance of the periodontium leads to the fact that the normal occlusal load turns into a traumatic factor that disrupts trophism and destroys its tissues [12]. In some cases, functional overload is compensated for a long time, and in some cases, the stage of decompensation quickly sets in. In the presence of a weakened periodontium, occlusal disorders that cause overload lead to an aggravation of the process and cause combined traumatic occlusion [13]. The displacement of the teeth is aggravated with an increase in the degree of bone resorption, while the degree of deformation of the walls of the alveoli increases, leading to a violation of microcirculation, and part of the periodontal fibers is compressed and does not participate in the depreciation of the masticatory load [14]. Therefore, the loads acting on the tooth should be distributed in physiological direction along the longitudinal axis of the tooth and be amortized by the periodontium. It has been established that the correction of the force vector by normalizing the occlusal relationships of the dentition due to selective grinding and rational prosthetics leads to the normalization of microcirculation in the periodontium [15]. It has been proven that the use of orthopedic measures aimed at eliminating or reducing periodontal overload creates conditions under which atrophic and inflammatory processes slow down, and medical and surgical treatment becomes more effective [6, 9, 10, 14]

To draw up a correct treatment plan for generalized periodontitis, an objective assessment of the clinical and functional state of the dentition is important. Various methods are used to examine periodontal tissues: visual, index, instrumental-functional and radiological. Clinical symptoms of periodontal disease are assessed and interpreted using standardized indices: inflammation (PMA, Massler, 1967; Loe & Silness 1963; plaque (Greene & Vermillion; 1960,1964); gingival sulcus bleeding (SBI Muhlemann & Cowell, 1971); papillary bleeding (PBISaxer & Muhlemann, 1971); Fuchs bone index; combinations of symptoms (Russel, 1967). However, the opinions of clinicians about the informativeness and reliability of clinical indices differ. To prevent the occurrence of errors during probing, the Florida probe system was created - an automatic probe with a constant pressure force for accurate determination of the depth of periodontal pockets and the level of attachment of the periodontal ligament. The results of the study are recorded in graphical form, indicators in millimeters and in color are displayed on the periodontal map. X-rays are widely used to assess the nature and degree of resorption of the alveolar bone other studies, including sighting and survey radiography (orthopantomography, computed tomography). Orthopantomography allows you to get a detailed planar image of the alveolar processes of the jaws, and three-dimensional tomography allows you to objectively and layer by layer assess the level of the bone from different sides of the tooth, excluding overlays and distortions. Functional methods include periodontal assessment with the Periotest device (Siemens). To the memory of V.A. Rumyantsev, periotestometry is an informative method for assessing the elasticity of the ligamentous apparatus of the tooth. The method also makes it possible to characterize the comparative effectiveness of various splinting methods. In addition to diagnosing structural changes in the periodontium, the problem of assessing the functional load acting on the dentition is extremely important, since the leading role of traumatic occlusion in the pathogenesis of periodontal diseases has been proven [4.5.8,12,13]. The possibility of diagnosing the functional overload of the periodontium and predicting the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment is impossible without assessing the occlusal relationship, since, according to a number of authors, occlusion has a direct impact on the function of the dentoalveolar system as a whole. using articulating paper, foil, wax in the oral cavity or on diagnostic models in the articulator. A relief imprint of occlusal contacts on a wax plate or silicone material for registration of occlusion can be used for primary visualization of supracontacts. However, the use of occludedograms is an insufficiently accurate static method [5.4]. For the qualitative and quantitative analysis of occludedograms, the researchers proposed various methods: visual, quasi-planimetric, occlusal sheet fluorescence, photocopying with control in polarized light, contact transfer to paper with a millimeter grid. However, no method can fully objectively reflect the state of occlusion, since it does not demonstrate the sequence of contacts, does not take into account the interaction of muscles and teeth, and also gives a signifi-

cant error [15]. Comprehensive analysis of occludedograms is possible on a scanning densitometer "Chromoscan-3" (Great Britain), which allows not only to obtain a graphic image of registries, but also to integrate the area and density of contacts [16,17]. Modern methods for assessing occlusion are based on the use of digital technologies. Thus, the method of computer photoanalysis of occlusion on plaster models is known [18]. AlignBracket3D computer programs (Align Bracket3D, 2008) have been developed to assess the quantity and quality of contacts; a method for determining the area of contacts using Adobe Photoshop software and Universal Desktop Ruler is also known. It is also proposed to use the CEREC 3 device (Sirona) for diagnostics, which makes it possible to determine and analyze the contacts of the teeth. The most informative data for assessing the occlusal load are provided by devices that register contacts using sensors that determine the pressure at the closure sites, taking into account the sequence of appearance and lifetime contacts. So, this is the "Occluzer" system, consisting of a bite plate (Dental rescale, Fuji Photo Film, Tokyo, Japan), a sensor sensitive to chewing pressure and an analyzing computer module (Occluzer, GCCorp., Tokyo, Japan). Occlusal contacts are displayed taking into account their area and pressure value, coded in different colors. The most widely implemented computerized occlusion analysis device in practice is the T-scan system, which is part of the Biopack diagnostic complex from Tekscan (Boston, MA). The method allows you to determine the sequence, synchronism of appearance, area and strength of each contact. To register the occlusal pressure and transfer information to the computer, a sensor is used - an ultrathin film "Mylar". The analysis is carried out on the basis of the recording of several (to clarify the data and eliminate errors) films that display the contacts of various types of occlusion. Recording is done in the following positions:

1. In the central ratio of the jaws to display the primary contacts of the rear contact position.
2. In the position of central occlusion to assess the forces of closure at the time of reaching multiple contacts.
3. When moving the lower jaw to assess contacts in dynamic occlusion.
4. In the position of habitual (actual) occlusion.

Interpretation of contact data is displayed in the form of color graphs - linear, planar and three-dimensional, as well as in the form of 3D visualization of the localization of contact points on a virtual model of the dentition (versions T-scan 8, 9). The use of computer analysis allows you to determine the state of the occlusal relationship of the dentition in several aspects: the degree of load and its distribution over the surface of the dentition (expressed as a percentage for each tooth or side of the dentition), identifying overload zones, assessing the balance of occlusion, identifying premature contacts. The precision T-scan system reliably determines both the force and the sequence of occlusion of antagonist teeth in static and dynamic occlusion. The overall assessment of occlusion is carried out according to three main parameters - the balance of occlusion in percent for each side of the dentition, the identification

of the strength and position of each contact, etc. "trajectories of forces" when reaching the maximum closure. Diagnosis is carried out before the start of treatment, during the correction of occlusion and after the end of treatment to monitor the results. The information value of the system lies in the ability to assess occlusion in combination with a functional assessment of muscles using the BioEMG myograph, which is part of the Biopack complex. . This is due to the fact that the stable position of the teeth of rigid models gives an occlusal pattern that is significantly different from the contacts that occur in the oral cavity with pathological tooth mobility.

References:

1. Grudjanov A.I. Zabolevanija parodonta / A.I. Grudjanov. – M.: Medicinskoeinformacionnoe agentstvo, 2009. – 334 s.
2. Zagorskij V.A. Okkluzija i artikuljacija: rukovodstvo / V.A. Zagorskij. – M.:BINOM, 2012. – 214 s.
3. Klineberg I. Okkluzija i klinicheskaja praktika / I. Klineberg, R. Dzhager; per.s angl.; pod obshh. red. M.M. Antonika. – 2-e izd. – M.: Medpress-inform, 2008. – 200 s.
4. Zolotareva Ju.B. Vlijanie okkluzionnyh narushenij na techenie vospalitel'nogo processa v tkanjah parodonta / Ju.B. Zolotareva, I.Ju. Guseva // Stomatologija. –2001. – No 4. – S. 21–23.
5. Skorova A.V. Kliniko-laboratornaja diagnostika i lechenie okkluzionnyh narushenij pri vospalitel'nyh zabolevanijah parodonta: Avtoref. dis. kand. med. nauk /Skorova Anna Vjacheslavovna; MMGSU. – M., 2009. – 122 s.
6. Smirnova A.V. Kompleksnoe lechenie pacientov s lokalizovannym parodontitom travmaticheskoy jetiologii / A.V. Smirnova, B.T. Moroz // Institut stomatologii. –2010. – No 1. – S. 70–74.
7. Sovremennye predstavlenija i razmyshlenija o kompleksnom lechenii zabolevanij parodonta / N.G. Abolmasov i dr. // Rossijskij stomatologicheskij zhurnal. –2009. – No 5. – S. 26–32.
8. Sovremennij vzgljad na problemu razrabotki programm profilaktiki zabolevanij tkanej parodonta / I.A. Belenova i dr. // Vestnik novyh medicinskih tehnologij. –2010. – T. HVII, No 2. – S. 163–165.
9. Grudjanov A.I. Zabolevanija parodonta i voprosy travmaticheskoy okkluzii v klinike ortopedicheskoy stomatologii / A.I. Grudjanov, N.A. Starikov // Novoe v stomatologii. – 1999. – No 4. – S. 3–18.
10. Belousov N.N. Osobennosti planirovanija kompleksnogo lechenija hronicheskogo generalizovannogo parodontita / N.N. Belousov // Materialy XV mezhdunarodnoj konferencii cheljustno-licevyh hirurgov i stomatologov «Novye tehnologii v stomatologii». – SPb., 2010. – S. 33–34.
11. Blankova S.L. Protokol vedenija bol'nyh s hronicheskim generalizovannym parodontitom G / S.L. Blankova N.A. Makarova // Prakticheskaja medicina (stomatologija) zhurnal dlja praktikujushchih vrachej. – 2009. – No 1(33). – S. 63–6
12. Voznaja I.V, Ron' G.I. Vlijanie ortopedicheskogo jetapa na rezul'taty lechenijavospalitel'nyh zabolevanij parodonta // Problemy stomatologii, 2005. – No1. – S. 5–7.
13. Shherbakov A.S. Rol' ortopedicheskogo lechenija v kompleksnoj terapii za -bolevanij parodonta/ A.S.Shherbakov, N.N.Belousov // Majestro stomatologii, 2008. –No3 (31). – S. 8–10.
14. Smukler H. Normalizacija okkluzii pri nalichii intaktnyh i vosstanovlen-nyh zubov / X. Smukler. — M.: Azbuka, 2006. – 136 s.